

Composite healing – A new perspective base on Bio-inspired helicoidal structure

Presenter: J.L. Liu

Summary

1. Introduction

- Healing of CFRP composites
- Bio-inspired helicoidal laminate

2. Methods and results

- CFRP/CFRTP hybrid
- CFRP with PA6 toughening/healing particles

3. Conclusion

Composite healing approaches:

- Embedding liquid healing agents contained in micro-capsule or vascular system in the composite.
- Embedding solid thermoplastic microparticles in the composite.

The challenge:

- Unable to heal damaged carbon fiber
- Impact-induced carbon fiber fracture is generally severe
- Carbon fibers are the main load carrier of CFRP

Bio-inspired helicoidal structure for CFRP laminate

- $[0/10/20/30/40/.....330/340/350/0]_s$
- Higher out-of-plane strength
- Higher impact resistance
- Unique damage pattern

single stack of chain bundles

epicuticle
exocuticle
endocuticle

Unique damage pattern of helicoidal laminate

0° inter-ply angle

Small inter-ply angle

Large inter-ply angle

90° inter-ply angle

Unique damage pattern of helicoidal laminate

- Spiralling matrix splitting
- Significant decrease in fiber damage
- Angle, ply thickness, matrix property dependant

CP47	$[(0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_T/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_T)_3/0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_T/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_T/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_T/0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E/(0^{\circ}_T/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_E/90^{\circ}_T/0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E)_3]$
SH47	$[0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E/-6^{\circ}_T/-12^{\circ}_E/-12^{\circ}_E/-18^{\circ}_T/-24^{\circ}_E/-24^{\circ}_E/.../-168^{\circ}_E/-168^{\circ}_E/-174^{\circ}_T/-180^{\circ}_E/-180^{\circ}_E]$
DH47	$[0^{\circ}_E/0^{\circ}_E/-12^{\circ}_T/-24^{\circ}_E/-24^{\circ}_E/-36^{\circ}_T/-48^{\circ}_E/-48^{\circ}_E/.../-156^{\circ}_E/-156^{\circ}_E/-168^{\circ}_T/-360^{\circ}_E/-360^{\circ}_E]$

SH47 after failure

DH47 after failure

CP47 after failure

CFRP with nylon toughening/healing particles

— Curing temperature — Curing pressure
 - - - Heating temperature - - - Healing pressure

(c)

(d)

QI: Quasi-isotropic layup; H6, H9, H18: Helicoidal laminates with 6°, 9°, 18° inter-ply angle

Conclusion

Laminates with helicoidal structure resist fiber damage

Helicoidal laminates with smaller inter-ply angle are more resistant to fiber damage

Nylon6 toughens the laminate interface and heals the damaged matrix

Helicoidal laminate with Nylon6 interlaminar toughening/healing agent has good mechanical performance and it can fully recover from a much higher impact energy after healing.

Thank you!